

Final report on dissemination & exploitation of results (D5.3)

Project	HORIZON-ZEN - EU research programme beneficiary depositing solution in Zenodo.
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Document history

Changes		
v1.0	2025-05-26	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Initial version

Executive summary

The HORIZON-ZEN project aimed to support EU research programme beneficiaries in complying with Horizon Europe's open science requirements by developing and promoting the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo. This final report provides an overview of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities.

The project successfully leveraged existing initiatives to maximise outreach despite limited resources available for dissemination and exploitation. Dissemination efforts included the creation of a project page and a Zenodo community, five newsletters, five blog posts, and participation in four major conferences and two webinars, including EU Open Data Days 2025. These activities reached an estimated 2,700 participants.

The EU Open Research Repository has over 21,000 uploaders and curators, and more than 12,000 EU projects have a research output shared on Zenodo. The repository's content had 4.5 million views and 7 million downloads per year. Engagement with early adopters resulted in over 2,100 EU projects onboarded.

Key results included the implementation of a branded portal and the distributed data curation framework. These features were co-designed with InvenioRDM partners and early adopters, and were broadly reused and most notably by the Biodiversity Literature Repository community.

Introduction

The primary objective of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities was to **stimulate the uptake of project results by EU programme beneficiaries** and to foster the integration of best practices among key target groups for exploitation. The full dissemination and exploitation plan is described in Deliverable 5.2¹ (D5.2). This document reports on the activities planned in D5.2 that have been carried out.

Constrained resources

The project operated with highly constrained resources, approximately 1 person-month (PM) dedicated to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, and 2 PM for working with early adopters. As a result, it relied heavily on dissemination activities carried out through existing initiatives beyond the project's direct scope. This report includes all such activities, not only those funded by the project.

¹ Nielsen, L. H., & Gonzalez Lopez, J. B. (2024). HORIZON-ZEN Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan (D5.2) (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246403>

Dissemination activities

Following is an overview of dissemination and communication activities that have been carried out. Please refer to the appendix for a detailed list of all activities.

Project website

A simple project page was created to communicate about the project. A dedicated project website was not established, as the primary communication channel was intended to be the EU Open Research Repository community once it launched. The project page supported the recruitment of early adopters and helped communicate the project's objectives to stakeholders.

Figure 1: Project page for the HORIZON-ZEN project.

Zenodo community

A Zenodo community² was created for the project and used to disseminate all research outputs in accordance with the data management plan and the open science practices described in the proposal. The project's deliverables published in the community received a combined total of 2,200 views.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/horizon-zen>

HORIZON-ZEN - D5.2 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan

Figure 2: HORIZON-ZEN's own Zenodo community serving dual use to also test our own features developed in the project.

Conferences and webinars

The project and EU Open Research Repository were disseminated at 4 conferences and 2 webinars reaching an estimated audience of 2,700 participants with the *EU Open Data Days 2025* being the most high-profile event. A training webinar for early adopters was held in May 2025 with training documentation provided on <https://help.zenodo.org>.

Figure 3: HORIZON-ZEN Exhibition booth at EOSC Symposium 2023.

Newsletters and blog posts

Zenodo’s main communication channel on Twitter unfortunately lost effectiveness after the platform was acquired and rebranded as X, resulting in a significant loss of our target audience. In response, we decided to launch a self-managed newsletter for Zenodo. However, this limited our reach, as the subscriber base had to be built from scratch. Project activities were disseminated through five newsletters, which received a total of 2,200 views, and five blog posts were published on the Zenodo, CERN, and OpenAIRE blogs.

User survey

A user survey was conducted in April 2025. Results were reported in D5.1 User feedback logbook³. The survey was sent to 674 users with a response rate of 12%. A bit more than 45% of the respondents had never used Zenodo or used Zenodo for less than 3 months, showing that the project has been able to attract new users.

Usage statistics of the EU Open Research Repository

Following are key usage statistics for the EU Open Research Repository obtained May 2025:

Measure	Value
Number of uploaders and curators in EU project communities	21,000 users
Number of EU projects with a record or community	12,000 projects
Views	4.5M per year
Downloads	7M per year

Exploitation of results

Sustainability plan

The Sustainability Plan⁴ (D5.5) for the HORIZON-ZEN project outlines the strategic approach to ensuring the sustainability of the EU Open Research Repository. The plan anticipates significant growth in data volume and user communities, suggesting automation and other strategies to manage increasing demands. Several elements suggested in the sustainability plan have been included in upcoming project proposals.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15476681>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393461>

Co-design with InvenioRDM partners, early adopters, and open science stakeholders

The design of features for the EU Open Research Repository was presented and discussed with the InvenioRDM community at four biweekly telecons and two annual workshops (see appendix), which helped align the design of the features to be usable and integrated into InvenioRDM for usage by all partners.

We have seen a large interest in all features developed for the EU Open Research Repository - examples include:

- Automated metadata checks: Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) has a Zenodo community and showed great interest in being able to specify extra metadata requirements (specifically validating if ASAP is a funder). We're working with the InvenioRDM community to build the necessary user interface for communities to self-manage the metadata checks and thus make it available to all 20,000 communities on Zenodo.
- Branding: We've had multiple requests for setting up branded portals on Zenodo. It still requires intervention from Zenodo staff to set it up, and we have so far not made it generally available as we need to carefully evaluate potential misuse and operational policies.
- Domain-specific vocabularies: We've received 10 requests for adding further domain-specific vocabularies to Zenodo in addition to GEMET, MeSH, EuroSciVoc, and EDMO.

iMagine project

An example of how we worked with early adopters is the [iMagine](#) project. We worked iMagine project participants on improving the EyeOnWater training dataset⁵. This included adding support for the GEMET vocabulary, improving the DCAT metadata export format to ensure all relevant information was properly included, and adding support for European Directory of Marine Organisations (EDMO) as organisational identifiers since many harbors do not have e.g. a Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifier. Several identified needs such as geospatial metadata could unfortunately not be addressed within the project.

Branded portals and distributed curation

The distributed data curation framework and the branded portal developed for the EU Open Research Repository were exploited for the Biodiversity Literature Repository⁶ (BLR) community on Zenodo as also described in the proposal as one of the exploitation use cases. The developed features allowed a branded portal to be set up in less than 1 week.

The distributed data curation framework was directly applicable to how BLR manages subprojects and delegates rights to manage subcollections within BLR. Similarly while the EU

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017143>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/biosyslit/>

Open Research Repository has collections for browsing by funding programme and subjects, BLR has collections for browsing by the taxa and specific collections to showcase parts of the repository.

Figure 4: Branded portal in Zenodo for the Biodiversity Literature Repository.

Figure 5: Collections and subcommunities reused by the Biodiversity Literature Repository.

Appendix

Dissemination and exploitation activities

Early adopters

Early adopters	# projects
Projects that requested an EU project community	415
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During pilot phase (March-October 2024) 	123
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After pilot phase (November 2024-May 2025) 	292
Existing projects invited to join	1,768
Total number of EU projects onboarded	2,183

Note that several of the early adopters also announced their participation (see examples below):

- <https://ocean-ice.eu/oceanice-early-adopter-of-the-eu-open-research-repository-pilot/>
- <https://classicaproject.eu/2024/10/classica-joins-the-eu-open-research-repository-on-zenodo/>
- <https://www.phoenix-he.eu/2025/02/phoenix-project-joins-the-eu-open-research-repository-on-zenodo/>
- <https://www.hybridplus.eu/index.php/hybridplus-joins-the-eu-open-research-repository/>

Conference and workshops

Conferences and workshops	Audience
EOSC Symposium 2023 (Exhibition booth) Nielsen, L. H., & Cancio, G. (2023, November 20). HORIZON-ZEN presentation at EOSC Symposium 2023. EOSC Symposium 23, Madrid, Spain. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159272	EOSC stakeholders 400 participants 125 views of slides
EnhanceR Symposium 2024 Nielsen, L. H. (2024, November 7). Building FAIR research repositories in practice. EnhanceR Symposium 2024, Dübendorf, Switzerland. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048101	EOSC and open science stakeholders 50 participants 12 views of slides
FAIRfest 2025 Gruenpeter, M., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., Hugo, W., L'Hours, H., Breitmoser, E., Ioannidis, A., Garijo, D., & Chue Hong, N. (2025, February 21). R for Reusability: Certification, metrics & guidelines	EOSC stakeholders 100 participants

for FAIR data and software - An interactive session: is FAIR enough?. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15015206	
EU Open Data Days 2025 Nielsen, L. H. (2025, March 19). The EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo – supporting the implementation of the EU open science policy. EU Open Data Days 2025, Luxembourg. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15055762 (recording).	Programme beneficiaries Open science stakeholders 250 in-person 2,000 online 61 views of slides

Newsletters

The Zenodo newsletter list was created in October 2023 in response to the change in ownership and name change from Twitter to X and following degradation of the platform for communication with target audience. Following newsletters included content for the EU Open Research Repository:

Newsletters	Views
Zenodo Newsletter December 2023 https://newsletters.zenodo.org/archive/2023-12	-
Zenodo Newsletter March 2024 https://newsletters.zenodo.org/archive/2024-03	182
Zenodo Newsletter June 2024 https://newsletters.zenodo.org/archive/2024-06	367
Zenodo Newsletter October 2024 https://newsletters.zenodo.org/archive/2024-10	587
Zenodo Newsletter April 2025 https://newsletters.zenodo.org/archive/2025-04	1060

Blog posts

Blog posts / news articles	Date
EU Open Research Repository Moves to Production https://blog.zenodo.org/2024/10/21/2024-10-21-production/	October 2024
Zenodo: 11 Years of Setting the Standards of Open Science Excellence! https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-11-years-of-setting-the-standards-of-open-science-excellence	August 2024
EU Open Research Repository	March 2024

https://blog.zenodo.org/2024/03/20/2024-03-20-eu-open-research-repository/	
The pilot of the new EU Open Research Repository stemming from the Zenodo community is launched today https://computing-blog.web.cern.ch/2024/03/the-pilot-of-the-new-eu-open-research-repository-stemming-from-the-zenodo-community-is-launched-today/	March 2024
CERN software to become central hub for EU research https://home.cern/news/news/computing/cern-software-become-central-hub-eu-research	January 2023

Webinars

Webinar	Participants / Audience
Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice - OpenAIRE webinar (July, 2024) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12712736 (recording).	177 / Programme beneficiaries 146 views of slides 272 views of recording
EU Open Research Repository Training Webinar (May 2025) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15479417	40 participants (76 registered)

Project deliverables

Deliverable	Views
FAIR-enabling deposit workflow design (D2.3) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10901185	899
Branded EC Zenodo-community design (D2.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199881	388
HORIZON-ZEN Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan (D5.2) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246403	160
Zenodo-communities for EU projects (2024-05-22) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11257907	157
Content and curation policy for the Zenodo-communities (D2.2) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419426	143

Sustainability plan for EU Open Research Repository (D5.5) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393461	129
Release and deployment strategy (D4.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099253	107
HORIZON-ZEN Data Management Plan (D1.2) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14245863	107
Project plan and monitoring framework (D1.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099189	106

InvenioRDM telecons/workshops

Event	Participants
InvenioRDM Telecon September 5, 2023: Presentation of branded communities design	28
InvenioRDM Annual Partner Workshop, March 2024, Münster (DE) FAIR-enabling deposit workflow design discussions	45
InvenioRDM Telecon, January 28, 2025: Presentation on collections and sub-communities features.	28
InvenioRDM Annual Partner Workshop, March 2025, Hamburg (DE) Integration of HORIZON-ZEN deliverables in InvenioRDM v13 release.	37
InvenioRDM Telecon, March 11, 2025: Presentation of automated checks RFC	29
InvenioRDM Telecon, February 11, 2025: Presentation of automated checks RFC	35